

THE ASSESSMENT OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE PROCESSES OF DEVELOPMENT OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN SCHOOL EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN (EXPERT SURVEY)

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Annotation.

The article reflects the results of a sociological study conducted on the method of expert assessment on the possibility of using foreign experience in the processes of development of human capital in school education in Uzbekistan. Feedback on the importance of international indicators in the assessment of the quality and effectiveness of school education in Uzbekistan is also described.

Keywords.

expert assessment, factory education style, modern competencies, international indicators, educational quality, PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, TALIS, educational technologies.

Introduction: In recent years, the leading countries of the world have been implementing in-depth and large-scale reforms in their educational systems. Because only a flexible and high-quality education system is a guarantee that the countries of the world will achieve challenges in socio-economic, cultural-political, spheres. It is no coincidence that the state, which is left out of the development trends that are taking place intensely and intensively, will lose its place in the conditions of fierce competition and market relations. It would be a wrong decision to stay away from new changes and innovations under these circumstances. So, in the words of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, education has already become a matter of Khayat Mamat. The reason is, one of the most important factors in the development of human capital is the field of Education. It is known that after the Second World War, countries like Japan and Germany, which suffered defeats and saw huge casualties, very quickly reached the stage of development in pictures. At the end of the 80s and the beginning of the 90s, they became the states with the most powerful economy in the world. According to the researchers, this is explained by the fact that both countries

allocated a large amount of investment from the state budget to the educational system and made an important decision to improve the quality of education and develop human capital.

The Japanese government, on the other hand, focused on the development of human capital in conditions of extremely limited natural resources and achieved the creation of the Japanese economic miracle. It is known that in Japan today the field of education is an area that is extremely supported by the state government. And in Singapore, one of the so-called Asian Tigers, the government covers 90% of the costs of its citizens in the field of high-tech learning and research.[1]

Also, Singapore has prioritized the development of school education primarily through Internet networking and enabling students to use the internet. In Singapore, schools are 100% connected to the Internet, and the school has established a link between biotechnics, and manufacturing businesses in multimedia, and the school that is, the school operates manufacturing businesses in the multimedia sector.[2] Such an experience is the only one in the world.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has also received several important regulatory legal acts on the development of school education, with a strong emphasis on the fields of Science and education. In particular, the Education Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan was revised and adopted in a new taxi on September 23, 2020, with some necessary amendments and additions following the requirements of the Times. Also, Section IV of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 60 of January 29, 2022 "on the development strategy of a new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026" is particularly relevant to the conduct of fair social policy, dedicated to the development of human capital. According to this document, it was established that global innovation consists in improving the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the index and entering the top 50 countries by 2030, as well as improving the position of Uzbekistan in terms of low indicators recorded in the Global Innovation Index.

Also, to improve the quality of education in schools, to bring the knowledge and qualifications of pedagogical personnel to an international level, and to establish local or international certification requirements in each subject for the functioning of the school. Continuing the work of filling secondary schools, especially educational institutions in remote areas, with pedagogical personnel with higher education. Further improvement of the system of appointment of the director and his deputies in schools with the provision of the participation of school teachers and parents. The system of public education is assigned such tasks as optimizing the activities of district divisions at the expense of full digitalization.[3]

From this point of view, the question of applying the achievements of developed foreign countries to the educational system of our country and developing proposals and recommendations on the study and solution of expert opinions on issues related to improving the place of our country in the international human development indexes shows the relevance of this study. Within the framework of the research work, in September - October 2022, a sociological study, and an expert survey was conducted to assess the possibilities of applying foreign experience in the processes of development of human capital in the Uzbek system of school education. A total of 12 experts participated in this survey³⁴. Of these, 7 were employees of Public Administration agencies and 5 were representatives of the academic circle. When selecting experts, their competencies and long years of work experience in this area were taken into account.

Figure 1. Experience of specialists who participated in the expert survey indicators, %.

Those with 10 years of seniority were 16%, those with 15 years of seniority were 33%, and those with 20 years and more were 51%. There are 8 males and 4 females. The median age of experts was 45 years.

The results of the study showed that despite the adoption of the above-mentioned laws and regulatory legal acts, there are currently several problems in the development of human capital in the system of school education in our country. As problems, the experts involved in the study expressed the opinion that educational technologies are outdated in schools in our country, education in most schools is based on more memorization, students are mainly taught to memorize and remember texts, rules, and numbers, and when it comes to supporting the

³⁴ Note: the expert survey involved 12 experienced practitioners working in the field of education as well as scientists conducting scientific research on these issues.

knowledge gained in life, the education system is missing, it is necessary to update educational methodologies. "How do you assess the importance of the educational system in the development of human capital in Uzbekistan?", all experts expressed their opinion on the importance of the educational sphere in the development of human capital, but the inability of the educational system in our country to fully meet the requirements of today, positive changes in the educational system, reforms should be carried out. We observed that experts who are representatives of the academic circle reacted much more sharply to this question than to the shortcomings of today's education if the experts acting in public administration offices approached it more softly.

According to most experts in the academic sphere, "the assessment of the state of the educational system in the development of human capital in Uzbekistan is a complex issue." Because in our country there were no serious scientific studies on this issue. The lack of serious scientific research in this area suggests that there is not enough attention to the educational system until Khali. Experts note that the importance of the educational system in the development of human capital in our country is not satisfactory, and this can be said about several factors. Firstly it can be seen that the educational system has little participation in the life of society and our ordinary life is not connected with science-secondly, TODAY Parents are spending more funds on weddings and dreams but when it comes to investing in the education of their children, they become a bee-eater.

Also, according to the general opinion of experts, the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan was initially invaded by Tsarist Russia, and later by the totalitarian Soviet regime, and for a long time experienced the colonial regime of the Soviet era, seriously affected the educational system of our country, and from this sphere of influence, it was noted that today's educational system They note that during the Soviet regime, in all states within the USSR, a factory style of education was used, that is, to work the general public in factories and factories, was trained. The educational system was also adapted for the cultivation of the working class. Everyone was taught in the same style, and mainly the lessons and teaching methodology were directed toward listening-that is, in schools mainly the teacher speaks, the lesson passes students are obliged to sit quietly and listen to the lesson. In such an educational system, knowledge is acquired mainly by listening and memorizing. The active participation of students in classes and the expression of free opinions and opinions has become a rare phenomenon. Over the years, students who were trained in this style were more likely to listen to the teacher in

the classroom and find it difficult when it comes to applying the knowledge gained to Real life

According to the opinions of Shukhrat Sattarov, director of the Republican Educational Center under the Ministry of public education, such a 20th-century style of factory education, which is unfortunately characteristic of the 20th century, has come is still coming without losing its priority in our educational methodologies. One of the disadvantages inherent in school education in our country is that it is not adapted to the application of the acquired knowledge in life. The reasons for the inconvenience of the educational system in our country can be seen in the fact that in schools students are not given practical skills if they are given knowledge. One of the main problems in Uzbek schools, the expert notes, is associated with a low level of life support for the knowledge gained at school. Human capital occurs mainly as a result of skills. The stage after knowledge is the stage of skills. The expert noted that the human factor also did not change since the content and methodology of education in Uzbekistan have not changed for fifty years. Textbooks and educational programs in our country have been created twenty years ago. According to her, the fact that the education system in our country is not harmonized with new technologies negatively affects the growth of the unemployment rate.

"Today the world is changing, technologies are changing, and the educational system cannot respond to this." The human factor does not change if we cannot bring modern changes to the field of Education. There will be development if the educational system is connected with the image of the social economic development of the state. So are we able to teach students to innovate those technologies in schools today? If we cannot bring those modern changes, and technologies to the field of education, we cannot change the human factor. As a logical continuation of expert opinions, it should be said that when the educational system is connected with modern technologies, it can deliver people to society and personnel to the cocktail market, which is suitable and inherent in the spirit of that time. That is, in a word, specialists and personnel who provide the country with their scourge are formed precisely at the school party. With the times, the school and educational system are required to keep up. From the answers given by experts to the first question, it can be concluded that the shortcomings and achievements in education do not immediately show their results. For example, the achievements and shortcomings in various areas of our society today can be called the derivative of Education received twenty or thirty years ago. In our opinion, the development of human capital is a concept that is inextricably linked with education.

The higher the quality of the educational system, the more effective the human capital and the benefits it brings if new modern knowledge and skills are integrated into education. We must not forget this when Hech. From the above points, it can be said that today it is necessary to teach modern competencies in Uzbek schools, characteristic of the 21st century. In our opinion, the main task of schools should be to prepare quality personnel for the cocktail market. Because there is a correlation between the unemployment rate and the education system. The more educated a person, the more modern knowledge and skills required in the 21st century, the more comfortable his marriage can be and competitive in the cocktail market.

In our opinion, to eliminate the factors that negatively affect the development of human capital in the above-mentioned system of school education, attention should be paid to the following mechanisms.

(See Figure 2)

Experts noted that the human factor is decisive in the achievement of development of any country in the 21st century, and the role of the educational system in the development of human capital is extremely important. So what is the level of quality of education in schools in our country today, it is better to determine it through the norms of international assessment. we turned to experts with the question:

According to Abduvali Ismailov, director of the National Center for the Implementation of international research on the quality of Education under the education inspectorate, reforms in the field of Education will be carried out and the focus on education at the government level and the involvement of resources will ensure that education in turn will be of good quality. The use of certainly prestigious international assessment criteria in determining and assessing the

quality level of Education will be the most reasonable solution in assessing the quality of education in our country. In recent years, special attention is paid to improving the quality of education in our country and improving it at the international level. On the way to this goal, the relevant documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan were developed. An example of this is the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 997 of 2018 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system". [4] With this decision, for the first time in its history, the issue of participation in international studies, including PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, and TALIS, has been identified as an urgent task in prestigious international studies internationally recognized in assessing the quality of education in countries of the world. The expert noted that if PISA evaluates the level of reading, mathematical and natural-scientific literacy of 15-year-old students, PIRLS

Evaluates the level of reading and understanding of the text of students in the 4th grade. The TIMSS International Assessment Program, on the other hand, assesses the level of mathematics and natural-scientific literacy of students in grades 4 and 8. PIRLS and TIMSS can be recognized as complementary programs. It is worth noting that the TALIS (Teaching and Learning International Survey) study, in contrast to the 3 studies listed above, is the largest international study aimed at assessing school directors and teachers in the general secondary education system based on a survey of school management style, social environment and conditions created for student education, as well as the educational environment in the school.

Why was it chosen to participate in these 4 International Studies in determining the quality indicators of secondary schools in our country? when asked, the expert replied as follows. In his opinion, these 4 international studies are the only programs that can give a full assessment of the functioning of the system and the level of quality of the 11th year of general secondary education. The results of this international study will be able to assess the level of educational quality in Uzbekistan. The indicators obtained through the results of these studies provide us with the opportunity to assess the level of knowledge of students in our country in reading, mathematics natural sciences. The expert noted that today, even according to the opinions of the leading experts of the world countries, the above-mentioned international studies are distinguished from other (indicators) assessment measures by being able to give the most appropriate assessment of activities in the sphere of Education. These studies make it possible to evaluate the most modern and necessary competencies. Since other experts also note the advantage of the above-

mentioned international assessment indicators, summarizing their opinion, it can be concluded that today the results of international studies such as PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, and TALIS have been considered the most effective methods in determining the quality of education in secondary schools of our country.

It is for this reason that, in our opinion, we can observe that the number of countries participating in these international studies is increasing from year to year.

Number of countries participating in the international study of PISA during 2000-2018 [5]

We can also see from this diagram that the number of countries participating in this international study is growing from year to year. There will also be no exaggeration to say that the countries of the world are defining their reforms and plans in the field of Education based on the results of these studies. Participation in these international studies and reforms carried out in the field of education in our country has paid off as much or can serve as a basis for concluding which deficiencies should be addressed in the future.

It is known that the formation of the Human Capital Index, which will be announced by the Bank of Jaxon, will be based on the results in the field of education and health. Also, the basis for the formation of this human capital index is the results of international studies such as PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS, and TALIS, which are mentioned above. According to expert Abduvali Ismailov, PISA is not a dogma, despite being a program that mainly evaluates mathematics, natural sciences, and reading literacy as a result of changing times, whichever science is of urgent importance, it proceeds to evaluate the same subject. At the end of the year, for example, the novelty was introduced that the logical and creative thinking of students was of urgent importance so Pisa evaluated creative thinking in 2022.

Financial literacy, and in 2025, a new direction of innovation was introduced, which is to evaluate the study of foreign languages. It also introduced a research and evaluation program called the Study of the digital world. The expert noted that as a result of studying the world experience and international research, it will be necessary to instill in our country the essence and methodologies of the content of international research into the educational process. This issue is a matter that requires a lot of effort and resources.

He believes that in our country there is a lack of educational methodological materials when conducting educational activities aimed not at memorizing international programs and students, but at developing competencies. Today, it will be necessary to instill the essence of the content of International Studies in educational processes and teach the skills and competencies required of students in the 21st century in school curricula. To implement this goal, educational materials, and didactic materials are being prepared in cooperation with foreign countries and international organizations. Uzbekistan's participation in international research aims to study international experience and create a national indicator of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has already begun to create a national assessment system based on the results of an international study. Headed by the National Center for the Implementation of international research on the quality of Education under the Educational Inspectorate, the Republic of Uzbekistan has participated in international PISA studies for the first time, and the result is expected to be published in 2023. At the same time, a national indicator for the happiness of school education is being developed in Uzbekistan and experimental testing is being carried out.

Summing up the opinions of experts on the above question, it can be concluded that to what extent the quality of school education in our country corresponds to the requirements of the International Assessment Standards in question is an extremely important issue.

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